

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPERATIVES FOR IMPROVING THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT OF THE LVIV REGION OF UKRAINE IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14420452>

Abstract

The research focuses on issues of state policy on formation and improvement of the region's investment environment. The relevance of the research results is that in the regions of Ukraine (including the rear) during the full-scale military invasion by the Russian Federation, the quality of the investment environment significantly deteriorated, which led to the loss of foreign investment, as well as a sharp reduction in the volume and activity of domestic investment. On the other hand, both the maintenance of the proper functioning of the regional economy and the post-war reconstruction of the regional economy are critically dependent on investments and infusions. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the imperatives of the regional policy to improve the investment environment of the Lviv region of Ukraine in the conditions of a high level of political, economic and social instability caused by the war. During the study, the following methods of analysis were used: grouping, logical analysis, strategic management (when assessing the quality of the system of state regulation of the development of the investment environment in the region), systematic analysis (for the purpose of developing organizational and economic means of the regional policy for the development of investment activity in the region), analytical and predictive calculations (for determining the directions of the regional policy of stimulating investment activity). The scientific novelty of the research results lies in the further development of the methodological and applied principles of substantiating the strategic priorities of the regional policy of improving the investment environment of the region in conditions of war.

Keywords: *region, regional development, regional policy, investment policy, investment, investment environment, investment attractiveness, imperatives, strategic goals, war, instability, crisis.*

The Lviv region of Ukraine is a region where the segment of alternative energy is actively developing (wind power plants in the Sambir, Drohobyt'sky and Turkiv districts, solar power plants in the Yavoriv and Zolochiv districts), which determines the high attractiveness of the region for European investors even during the war and constant Russian attacks on energy infrastructure of the country. Yes, during 2021-2024 the Czech company MND invested 61.5 million euros in the construction of the most powerful Oriv wind power plant in the west of Ukraine on the Carpathian ridge between the villages of Oriv and Zimivka of the Truskavet territorial community. Today, this power plant provides about 5% of the electricity consumption of the Lviv region. An additional benefit from such an investment project was the creation of new jobs, improvement of roads to nearby settlements and an increase in the flow of tourists in these territories.

Taking into account the development potential of the region is critically important when forming a proactive investment policy in Ukraine, because it allows defining a coherent and consistent strategy, aimed at economic and social growth, strengthening the security and stability of territories in the face of the latest challenges. Taking into account the development potential allows investors to make investments in promising industries and strategically important objects of the region, which corresponds to the concept of impact investing. The application of this approach involves a

new way of investing, which is not only aimed at obtaining economic benefits, but also at solving certain social problems (social and/or environmental). The idea of the social significance of investment can be considered as part of the movement for sustainable development, because the positive impact of investments on society and the environment is taken into account. This approach must be used when choosing strategic guidelines for improving the environment for business development and attracting new investment resources, which, in the meantime, contributes to the creation of new jobs, and as a final result - to increase the level and quality of life of the population of the region.

It is clear that a proactive investment policy and prospects for the development of impact investing in Ukraine depend on the conditions of the investment market, the specifics of capital formation, their free use and protection, the availability of infrastructure, human resources, the quality of institutional support, etc. And in the spatial aspect, the security type of the territory plays an important role (rear, support, temporarily occupied territories, combat zones), functional type of territory (recovery territories, regional poles of growth, regions with special conditions for development, territories of sustainable development), the development of cross-border relations and the absence of international border conflicts. It is obvious that the consequences of the war have become less noticeable for the so-called rear regions, however, there are also processes of in-

creasing social vulnerability of the population, a decline in business and investment activity, a reduction in consumer demand and the capacity of the domestic market, ultimately - a decrease in the population. All this indicates a total crisis of preservation of the catalysts of economic growth.

Therefore, stable regional poles of growth should be formed for faster post-war recovery of the economy and strengthening of the economic (especially investment) security of the state. Considering the Lviv region as a dynamic (in its own way), rear, innovative and informationally active region with high mobility of population and capital, as well as a border territory with the EU with close foreign economic and investment ties, it is worth identifying the key prerequisites for the formation and improvement of the investment environment of this region, in particular:

1. Simplification of administrative procedures and reduction of bureaucratic barriers for investors.

2. Development of infrastructure, in particular transport networks, communications and energy (especially in mountainous areas), which will increase the attractiveness of the region for investments.

3. Improvement of institutional and organizational support of regional investment policy in the conditions of war and post-war reconstruction

4. Creation of support programs for local enterprises and entrepreneurs, which will contribute to the creation of new jobs and increase of business activity in the region.

5. The development of the education system and the improvement of the qualifications of the workforce, which will help to ensure the growth of innovative and creative potential and the strengthening of the competitiveness of the region (given its close cross-border and interterritorial cooperation with European countries).

6. Balancing the regional labor market and preserving the personnel potential of the region for efficient and timely execution of works within the limits of investment projects (the problem remains high migration activity in the region, a shortage of narrow-profile specialists and qualification disparities in the labor market)

7. Ensuring military-political stability and economic security of the state and, accordingly, the region.

The presence of these prerequisites makes it possible to form a favorable economic, organizational-institutional and image base for the development of the investment environment of Lviv Oblast, which affects the pace of economic growth and determines the potential of the post-war recovery of the region. In this context, the Lviv region has a chance to become a "locomotive" of the European integration process through the rapid reconstruction and convergence of various components of the economic system with the corresponding European components. Taking into account the above provisions, the key prerequisites, goals and tasks of improving the investment environment of the Lviv region should be considered in the focus of two strategic priorities: stabilization of the economy and post-war recovery.

In our opinion, under the current conditions, it

seems more rational to apply the strategy of phased implementation of the regional investment policy, when the first stage is about stabilizing the situation and restoring the stability of the economy (priority I), and the second - about restoring competitive advantages and directly increasing the investment attractiveness of the region in basic (traditional) and new strategic segments (priority II).

Such a vision seems to be the most optimal, although one should take into account the objective impossibility of clearly identifying the terms of the implementation of the relevant stages and the achievement of systemic changes in view of the uncertainty of the course of the war in Ukraine and its potential impact on the socio-economic system of the regions. At the same time, contrary to this circumstance, the implementation of regional investment policy measures aimed at achieving the strategic goals of improving the investment environment and strengthening the investment capacity of the region should be carried out already now, in the realities of war, because due to the consequences of hostilities against the background of systemic defects of the economy (inefficient management, corruption, informal employment, vulnerability of the monetary and financial system, etc.), both the country and the region continue to lose human and investment potential.

It is absolutely obvious that the implementation of a new investment policy in the conditions of spatial disintegration and numerous crises in Ukraine should begin with overcoming their consequences, as well as existing and potential challenges. In view of the above, as part of the strategic priority of stabilizing the economy of the Lviv region, it is first of all important to focus on solving such tasks as strengthening security and defense capabilities, as: the development of investment in military-tech startups and the construction of military-industrial complex enterprises.

A full-scale war in Ukraine stimulates the development of military technologies and innovations. A significant competitive advantage of the Lviv region in this area is a developed IT cluster, which allows to successfully combine artificial intelligence and military technologies. One of the examples of successful cooperation of IT specialists from different regions and military experts was the development of a system for collecting and analyzing data on enemy positions and movements called Griselda, which will be used by the defense units of Ukraine from 2022. It should be noted that it is an important tool for the spread of such and other similar innovations there is communication between government structures, business and developers at regular hackathons and meetups dedicated to defense technologies. At the same time, state and private investors play a key role in promoting development. It is the state that should primarily promote the activation of grant support for military-tech startups and cyber security developments in Ukraine. Moreover, this issue is institutionally ensured by the Ukrainian Startup Fund, created in 2018 at the initiative of the Minister of Finance of Ukraine and transferred from 2023 to the sphere of management of the Ministry of Digital Trans-

formation of Ukraine. During its existence, the fund financed almost 400 startups with a total value of 8.7 million dollars. USA. The share of the sector of military technologies and innovations among all financed projects is small, so the development of this area is considered promising, and the Lviv region can become the driver of the mentioned processes. By the way, it is also worth mentioning the only public private fund that invests in Ukrainian defense startups - D3 Venture Capital. The amount of support of this fund is much larger and amounts to tens of millions of dollars. USA. At the regional level, in order to successfully attract and operate investment projects in the Lviv region, it is necessary to expand the network of advisory bodies to solve any problematic issues of investors in the process of their activities, to search for additional sources of investment, as well as to establish cooperation between central authorities and local self-government bodies in ensuring proper business functioning conditions. Currently, the main consultative and advisory functions in this area are performed by the Investor Support Service under the Lviv Regional Military (State) Administration.

To meet the needs of the Ukrainian army, an extremely important aspect today is the construction of military-industrial complex enterprises that specialize in the production of military equipment, weapons and other military equipment. If the primary task of stabilizing the country and regions should be to increase the defense capacity of the state, then such enterprises should appear precisely in the west of Ukraine with the financial support of the government. It is worth noting that a number of industrial complex enterprises operate in the Lviv region, however, in wartime, the state should more actively support these business entities and contribute to increasing their capacity. We are primarily talking about the Lviv State Plant "LORTA", the Lviv Armored Plant, Lviv State Aviation Repair Plant, State Research Enterprise "Conex", Lviv Research Radio Technical Institute. An important step is also the development of additional regional support programs for enterprises producing military goods.

Despite the fact that Lviv Oblast is one of the most competitive and promising regions of the country, there is a need to transform the focus of the industrial policy of the region from a sectoral vector to a territorial one in order to create a new image of Lviv Oblast in general and its individual communities as a territory of favorable investment environment, high competitiveness, innovative technologies, economic freedom and well-being. Moreover, in wartime conditions, the emphasis shifts, as already noted, towards the development of the military industry and related industries related to cyber security, logistics networks, prosthetics and military rehabilitation. It follows that the so-called new industrialization is the target reference point during the implementation of the structural transformation of the real sector of the economy (in particular, industry) of the region.

This model combines elements of reindustrialization and neoindustrialization, the advantages of which are diversification of the industrial sector, ensuring a high level of import substitution, and the formation of

competitive exports. In addition, new industrialization as a modern economic policy of the regions requires selective approaches to the influence of the regional government and local governing bodies (level of territorial communities) on the transformation of the industrial and technological base, because the insufficiently effective use of the industrial and technological potential of the regions, in particular the Lviv region, leads to an increase in import dependence, a decrease in investment activity, and an inadequate response to the increase in domestic demand. Improving the situation requires flexible and up-to-date mechanisms for the transformation of regional industrial policy, for example, with resources for the economic mobility of business, through the creation of industrial parks and the development of clusters to attract investment in the real sector.

In accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Industrial Parks", a unified register of industrial parks has been created in Ukraine to provide business representatives, managing entities, participants of industrial parks and other interested parties with the necessary state support. According to the state register, as of the beginning of 2023, 10 industrial parks in various sectors of the economy were registered in the Lviv region, and by the beginning of 2024, their number increased to 15, which is almost 17% of all domestic parks.

Practically all industrial parks in the country, including those in the Lviv agglomeration, have difficulties attracting participating residents. This explains the small number of actually operating parks (4 out of 15 in the region).

The main task of the construction of industrial parks as special industrial territories of the Lviv region is to create a favorable environment for attracting direct investments to the region and stimulating the growth of the local and regional economy. The tasks and objectives of the park operation declared in the relevant concepts must be achieved thanks to:

(1) infrastructure development (construction of roads, water supply systems, power grids, Internet communication and other necessary communications);

(2) a high level of service (access to infrastructure that meets business needs, business support services, access to logistical and technical resources, as well as facilitation of interaction between enterprises and authorities);

(3) introduction of tax benefits or holidays (complete exemption from taxes on land and real estate);

(4) application of resource-saving technologies.

As a result, foreign and domestic investors get easier access to plots equipped and prepared for industrial use with the necessary engineering and technical infrastructure, which makes it possible to minimize costs for the organization of high-tech production in the territory of the Lviv region. In general, the creation and full functioning of industrial parks in the region will make it possible to significantly increase its competitiveness in attracting and developing investments, as well as allow the implementation of the key principles of the new industrialization policy.

Support of industrial parks is also important from the point of view of creating new jobs as another factor

in increasing the investment attractiveness of individual communities and the region as a whole. However, among many advantages and expected prospects, there is a significant institutional gap that inhibits the development of special industrial territories in Ukraine. We are talking about the practical application of the tax benefits provided by the law for initiators and participants of industrial parks. Thus, the provision of such benefits may contain signs of state aid provided to economic entities. However, despite the fact that state aid programs provide an opportunity to offer business entities, which will implement investment projects, a specific list of forms and the amount of state aid at the expense of the local budget during the specified period, to date no program of state aid to initiators of creation (business entities), management companies and participants of industrial parks has been formed and agreed with the Antimonopoly Committee at the expense of local budgets. In other words, despite the incentives provided by the legislation, the practical possibility of their use is still limited, since the local government does not have a mechanism for implementing these incentives. This means that the institutional component of ensuring the investment policy of the state and regions must be revised.

Another important task of improving the investment environment of the Lviv region in the focus of economic stabilization is increasing economic freedom. Of course, this issue is primarily considered and resolved at the national level by optimizing the tax system and countering the shadowing of the economy. Experts believe that the tax system, built on stable tax legislation, is the main determinant of the formation of a favorable investment climate in the country and the attractiveness of its regions. Therefore, simplifying or reducing the tax burden on business (especially on small and medium-sized ones) has a direct impact on the development of entrepreneurship and investment activity in the country and regions. No less effective measures can be applied at the regional level, in particular, reducing bureaucratic obstacles related to administration and the duration of procedures necessary to obtain permits for the implementation of one or another economic activity. I finally, another step on the way to increasing economic freedom in the Lviv region should be the encouragement of foreign innovations through the creation of a system of incentives for the development of technological startups and innovative projects. In addition to direct methods of influencing the level of economic freedom, it is also worth considering indirect measures related to the expansion of the region's foreign trade relations. It is primarily about more active participation in international trade agreements and the intensification of export-import operations to increase the sales markets of Ukrainian products. The implementation of the listed measures will contribute to attracting investments, economic progress and increasing the well-being of the population of the region.

In the context of the post-war reconstruction of the economy of the Lviv region, the main task, in our opinion, should be the determination of structural investment priorities. This means a clear identification of the priority areas of development of the region's economy

and provision of conditions for attracting investment resources in these areas. Domestic and foreign investors should have a clear understanding of which sectors of the economy are priority for the region and what measures are taken to support their development. One of the proposals for strengthening organizational and institutional support for the prioritization of economic sectors in accordance with the specifics of the region and the challenges of wartime we determined the need to develop a regional base of investment projects (on the example of Lviv region), aimed at shifting the structure of the region's economy in the future by reducing the share of traditional (raw materials-oriented) industries (metallurgy, chemical industry, energy) and increasing the share of industries that produce competitive products with a high level of added value. At the central level, in 2024, the Unified portfolio of public investment projects for 2025 was created, approved by the newly created Strategic Investment Council. The selection of investment projects that will receive funding from the state budget was carried out on the basis of a number of criteria, among which the strategic relevance of the projects was determined first. It is advisable to apply a similar approach when creating the regional base of investment projects proposed above, which would be primarily useful for foreign and domestic investors.

The restoration of the priority basic branches of the economy of the Lviv region, as a component of the system of ensuring the investment attractiveness of the region, involves strengthening the support of high-tech sectors, which are actively developing today within the framework of Industry 4.0, as well as industries with a high export potential or a significant impact on the regional and national economy. Among such industries, it is worth noting the computer industry and areas related to artificial intelligence, the production of equipment, the electronic industry, the aviation sector, the military industry, alternative energy, agriculture and the processing of agricultural products, the development of infrastructure, etc. A key role in the spread of progressive technologies in the region and the country in general is played by the powerful Lviv IT Cluster, which in 2023 joined the UN Global Compact – the world's largest community of responsible businesses. This certainly creates a positive investment image of the Lviv region and reinforces its status as a regional pole of growth.

In addition to the basic sectors of the economy, the recovery of the region should take place at the expense of the development of strategic branches of smart specialization, which were defined in the regional development strategy of the Lviv region for 2021-2027, developed in accordance with the current regulatory and legal acts of the government. An extremely positive step in this direction was the official joining of Lviv Oblast to the European Smart Specialization Platform (S3 Platform) in 2021, which, among other things, was planned within the scope of the tasks of the current State Regional Development Strategy (operational goal V "Sustainable development of industry"). Such a step significantly expands the region's access to European funding instruments and creates new opportunities to

involve foreign partners in post-war reconstruction. Accordingly, according to the results of numerous expert studies, presented in the updated regional development strategy of the Lviv region, the strategic priorities of the smart development of the region are defined as "Bioeconomy" (organic agriculture, food, woodworking, furniture, printing industry and bioenergy), "Creative industries" (IT, design, fashion, audiovisual art, architecture, publishing and jewelry manufacturing), "Industry with high added value" (engineering and instrument building, textile industry), as well as medicine, health and recreation (so-called "medical tourism").

No less important target orientation in the post-war perspective of the region is the promotion of greening and green investments. Promotion of sustainable development and protection of the environment is a significant factor in attracting investments - especially for solving the biggest environmental problems of the region, related to deforestation, waste disposal and environmental damage from the activities of the mining industry. Of course, the western regions of Ukraine were less affected by military operations, because such great damage to natural ecosystems as in the eastern-southern regions is not observed here. However, local industrial enterprises, in the conditions of a difficult economic situation, do not always adhere to ecological principles of activity. This affects the increase in the volume of waste in the region, which enters the environment and pollutes the soil and water bodies, and also leads to the uncontrolled consumption of natural resources without their restoration.

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